

NUMERICAL RESPONSE OF THE COHESIVE LAW AT THE CONTACT SURFACE BETWEEN NATURAL YARNS AND LIME-BASED MORTAR.

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ABSTRACT

Over the last two decades innovative composite materials have received a great attention as external retrofitting solutions for masonry structures. In particular, NTRM (Natural Textile Reinforced Mortar) composite materials have shown potential as novel alternative strengthening systems, thanks to their sustainability, recyclability and cost-effectiveness. Several documents have assessed their mechanical performance through direct tensile tests or shear bond tests on masonry substrate. In addition, many studies have demonstrated their efficiency in terms of resistance increase by means of full-scale applications. Nevertheless, the bond behaviour between natural yarns and mortar needs to be examined in more depth. For this purpose, a series of pull-out tests are carried out to investigate the stress transfer between a single natural yarn and the inorganic lime-based mortar. In detail, the bond behaviour of two different natural yarn types (flax and jute) will be presented and analysed. After this, the bond-slip response curves experimentally derived are used to calibrate a surface-based cohesive contact model in a non-linear finite element framework. Considerations on how exposure to aggressive environments can affect the mechanical performance of natural fibres are also made.

KEYWORDS

natural composite; sustainability; retrofitting; cohesive law; numerical analysis; durability; alkaline treatment;

INTRODUCTION

Over the time, existing buildings have been damaged owing to hazard events across the world. Different technologies for the rehabilitation of existing reinforced concrete and masonry structures have been developed. Among these, in the last decade, TRM (Textile Reinforced Mortar) composites have been successfully applied for the strengthening of masonry constructions. These innovative materials represent an excellent solution for the retrofitting of heritage structures, thanks to their compatibility with the substrates due to vapour permeability, increased sustainability and reversibility of the intervention. The main advantage of these systems is their versatility related to the possible use of different fiber materials, among which natural fibers have been receiving great attention as a more sustainable alternative to replace synthetic fibers. Natural fibers are low cost, renewable and biodegradable [1-4]. Moreover, recent studies have demonstrated the suitability of natural fibers as reinforcement for TRM strengthening systems [5-9].

Thus, this research will focus on a new generation of sustainable, cost-effective, efficient strengthening solutions by using environmentally friendly natural fibers meshes embedded in an inorganic lime-based mortar matrix, referred to as 'NTRM' (Natural Textile Reinforced Mortar). The feasibility of the application of natural fiber – based TRM is demonstrated in [9], where a case study application is presented.

Although an increasing number of experimental and analytical studies are available regarding the mechanical behavior of TRM composites, limited work has been done to investigate NTRM mechanical performance, also as strengthening for masonry structures [11-14]. In [11] the mechanical performance of basalt-based TRM is investigated, while in [13-15] the mechanical response of flax-based or jute-based TRM is assessed. The tensile response of flax-TRM composites and their effectiveness are also studied in [16]. In [17] it was experimentally demonstrated that the use of flax-based TRM as

strengthening of masonry walls subjected to diagonal compression can lead to an increase in capacity of about 118%. Although NTRMs have been proven to be an effective solution for structural applications, their durability is still an open issue, which is fundamental to guarantee their long-term effectiveness.

The aim of this study is to fill this research gap and to investigate the bond developed at the interface [18-19] between natural yarns and the mortar matrix. This would help in the evaluation of the intrinsic properties of NTRM systems. The τ -slip behaviour of single flax and jute yarns embedded in the same lime-based mortar, is experimentally tested through a series of pull-out tests. After this, the contact at the yarn to mortar surface is simulated in a non-linear finite element model, through an adhesion law. The bond models could be used for the design of more effective strengthening solutions.

Finally, the possible damage to the natural yarn during the mortar curing period is evaluated, providing valuable insights into the deterioration caused by exposure to the alkaline environment.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Two NTRM systems are examined in this study: both of them are made with the same type of lime-based mortar, which is combined in turns with flax (Figure 1.a) and jute (Figure 1.b) textiles. These textiles are not yet available in the market. The mechanical properties of the lime-based mortar are assessed by means of flexural and compressive tests. Then, the geometrical and mechanical characteristics of the textiles are determined. In detail, after the density and the cross section calculation of both natural fibres, the tensile behaviour of each single yarn is assessed through direct tensile tests.

Figure 1.a Flax textile

Figure 1.b Jute textile

Materials characterization

Flexural and compressive properties of the mortar

Along with the technical data sheet provided by the supplier, the properties of the mortar (named with 'K-LIMEDO') used in this research are assessed through flexural and compressive tests using a universal electromechanical testing machine, according to EN 1015-11 Annex B (2019) [20]. The tests were conducted at an age of 180 days from casting. The strains for the flexural tests were calculated from the displacements recorded by 2 LVDTs connected to a yoke mounted on each mortar prism (40mm x 40mm x 160mm) [Figure 2.a]. The results are collected in Table 1, in terms of tensile strength (f_t), Young's modulus (E_t) and compressive strength (f_c).

Determination of the density and the cross section of the single yarns

In order to define the properties of the natural fibres, referred to as K-FLAX-NC (for flax textile) and K-JUTE-NC (for jute textile), characterization of their density was necessary. For this purpose, the 'ASTM D8171-18: Test method B – Bouyancy (Archimedes)' method was adopted [21] in conjunction with 'BS EN ISO 1889:2009: Reinforcement yarns - Determination of linear density' to estimate their cross section [22].

Determination of mechanical properties of the single yarns

A bespoke clamping system using guide rollers with a relatively large radius was used to determine the main mechanical characteristics such as Young's modulus, failure stress and the corresponding strain, of single yarns extracted directly from the textile mesh. This setup was employed to avoid stress concentrations in the gripping area and eliminate the need of bonded tabs [18-19] (see Figure 2.b) [23,

24]. A traditional measurement system is used along with a contactless measuring method. For this last one, small spherical markers were attached to the natural cord specimen at different locations. Their displacements were detected by a laser LVDT and also through a high definition camera with an appropriate frequency of images acquisition, dependant on the test rate ('Point-Tracking' contactless method). The tensile behaviour in terms of stress and strain are reported in the Figures 3.a and 3.b.

Figure 2.a: Flexural test on mortar prism

Figure 2.b: Direct tensile test on single natural yarns

Figure 2.c: Pull-out test on natural yarn embedded in mortar

$$\tau = F / A_{cyl} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where:

τ = adhesion at the reinforcement-to-mortar surface [N/mm²]

F = global load [N]

A_{cyl} = external surface of the single cord [mm²]

$$\text{Slip} = \text{relative displacement} - \varepsilon_{steel} \cdot d \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where:

Relative displacement = displacement recorded between the unbonded portion of the cord and the surface of the mortar cube [mm]

ε_{steel} = steel strain detected by the laser method [%]

d = distance between the reference marker and the surface of the mortar [mm]

Table 1: Inorganic mortar matrix properties (average values)

Mortar	Label	f_t^* [N/mm ²]	f_c [N/mm ²]	E_t [kN/mm ²]
Lime-based mortar	K-LIMEDO	3.5	11.2	1.5

* indirect tensile test

Figure 3.a Direct tensile tests on ‘K-FLAX-NC’ single yarns (Stress-strain (σ - ϵ) response curves)

Figure 3.b Direct tensile tests on ‘K-JUTE-NC’ single yarns (Stress-strain (σ - ϵ) response curves)

Table 2: Single yarn physical and mechanical properties (average values)

Textile	Label	Density ρ [g/cm ³]	Cross section [mm ²]	f_t [N/mm ²]	E_t^{**} [kN/mm ²]
Flax	K-FLAX-NC	1.495	0.067	384.0	6.2
Jute	K-JUTE-NC	1.383	0.193	157.2	4.3

** Secant stiffness of the elastic phase (20%-50% range of the stress peak).

Pull-out tests

The casting of the specimens was made using a bespoke acrylic frame. Each single natural yarn was maintained in vertical position by fitting the yarn through a central hole placed at the base of the mould and fixing it to a transverse bar to guarantee their alignment. The natural yarn was embedded for the entire cube height of 50mm. These tests were carried out using an electromechanical universal testing machine with a maximum capacity of 10kN (Figure 2.c) under displacement control with a loading rate of 1.2mm/min. The load and global measurements were acquired by the load cell and the LVDT integrated in the testing machine. The relative displacement (slip) between the cord and the mortar cube was detected using the ‘Point Tracking’ method. The strain of the cord was also calculated using the contactless system, over different measurement lengths. The local elongation of the un-bonded portion of the cord was also measured with a laser LVDT. Therefore, the reliability of data is ensured thanks to the combination of traditional and non contact methods. Finally, two formulations are used to display the experimental results in terms of τ -slip. The first one (Eq. 1) is used for the adhesion ‘ τ ’, meanwhile the second (Eq. 2) for the slip calculation. The response curves are shown in Figure 4.a and Figure 4.b.

Figure 4.a Pull-out experimental response curves for ‘K-FLAX-LIMEDO-NC’

Figure 4.b Pull-out experimental response curves for ‘K-JUTE-LIMEDO-NC’

Table 3: Pull-out experimental results (average values)

NTRM	Label	τ_{max} [N/mm ²]	Slip at τ_{max} [mm]	Bond Stiffness ¹ [N/mm]	Bond Stiffness ² σ/ε [kN/mm]
Flax and lime-based mortar	K-FLAX-LIMEDO-NC	0.06	0.4	0.15	4.5
Jute and lime-based mortar	K-JUTE-LIMEDO-NC	0.16	1.5	0.11	3.34

¹ Secant stiffness of the elastic phase of the load-slip curve.

² Secant stiffness of the elastic phase of the σ - ε curve.

NUMERICAL SIMULATION

The experimental outcomes reported in the previous paragraphs were used to calibrate a numerical model by means of a non-linear finite element analysis software [18-19]. The geometry (Figure 6.a) of the specimen was simulated using 3D elements (Figure 6.b) and the materials properties were those obtained from the experimental tests. The relative governing parameters were obtained by implementing an inverse analysis approach. Then, the bond-slip law was determined between the external surface of the yarn and the surrounding mortar. Despite an initial response dominated by adhesion, the overall NTRMs bond could be identified as a linear behaviour (Figure 7.a and Figure 7.b).

Figure 6.a Focus on the experimental pull-out set-up

Figure 6.b FE model and boundary conditions

Figure 7.a Numerical (blue coloured line) and experimental τ -slip (τ -S) responses (greyscale lines) for 'K-FLAX-LIMEDO-NC'

Figure 7.b Numerical (red coloured line) and experimental τ -slip (τ -S) responses (greyscale lines) for 'K-JUTE-LIMEDO-NC'

RESULTS DISCUSSION

The behaviour observed for the two systems are similar and highly dependent on the natural origin of these reinforcements. Despite a very short stiffer behaviour, the global curve responses could be assumed as linear. Indeed, for the system made with flax yarn (Figure 4.a) and lime-based mortar a maximum value of bond strength is about 0.06N/mm^2 corresponding to a slip of 0.45mm . For the NTRM with jute yarn and the same mortar (Figure 4.b), the maximum bond strength is equal to 0.15N/mm^2 with a slip of 1.5mm . As reported in both experimental τ -slip graphs (Figg. 4.a and 4.b), it seems that an initial adhesion, even if negligible, can be developed between the yarn and the surrounding mortar. In an attempt to assess the possible degradation of the tensile and bond properties of the yarn caused by exposure to the surrounding mortar [1, 25], the response of yarns embedded in mortar was compared to that of single yarns of flax and jute textiles exposed to an alkaline environment for 1000-hour, as well as unconditioned yarns (Table 4).

NTRM with flax reinforcement

From this evaluation, the peak value of bond achieves the tensile maximum stress of the yarns conditioned after 1000-hour period in alkakine environment at 40degrees. In this case a reduction of 85% in maximum load capacity was observed when compared to unconditioned yarns. In addition, it should be noted that during the pull-out tests, after the sudden loss of strength, additional slip was recorded in conjunction with negligible strain being developed along the unbonded part of the yarn, thus suggesting the occurrence of a telescopic failure within the mortar.

NTRM with jute reinforcement

The comparison in terms of stress-strain curve responses between the pull-out tests and the direct tensile tests of the unconditioned jute yarns has demonstrated that the final shear stress is equal to the average value of stress reported for the conditioned yarns under alkaline environment for a 1000-hour period at 24 degrees. The average loss in strength is around 57%. Indeed, even with a lower decrease in percentage than the flax, the jute yarns appears more susceptible to the alkaline environment.

Table 4: Mechanical properties after alkakine treatment (average values)

Textile	Label	Conditioned $f_{tensile}$ [N/mm ²]	Unconditioned $f_{tensile}$ [N/mm ²]	Unconditioned f_{bond} (Eq.3) [N/mm ²]
Flax	FLAXK- ALK1k-40D ⁺	49.4 ⁺	384.0	41.1
Jute	JUTEK-ALK1k-24D [!]	66.9 [!]	157.2	64.6

⁺1000-hour period in alkaline treatment at 40°C

[!]1000-hour period in alkaline treatment at 24°C

$$f_{bond} = F/A \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

f_{bond} = bond (Pull-out tests) stress of the natural yarn [N/mm²]
 A = cross section [mm²]

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The work presented in this study is part of a larger experimental and numerical programme examining the bond behaviour of several strengthening systems comprising natural textile with lime-based inorganic matrices. Based on the results presented above, the following conclusions can be drawn.

Natural yarn and lime-based mortar. The alkaline environment over the curing period could affect the bond behaviour at the interface between the single natural yarn and the mortar. After a short contribution of the adhesion at the very beginning, a telescopic failure could be identified within the composite under (pull-out) shear behaviour, due to the damage of the fiber. This is in turn, affects the

development of any significant chemical adhesion and adequate mechanical bond between the yarn and the surrounding matrix. To overcome this drawback, it should be suggested an appropriate coating for the impregnation of the natural fiber against the basic attack and for improving their stiffness. Therefore, it is also necessary in studying a correct architectural design for the textile mesh to allow the interlocking between the reinforcement and the inorganic mortar-matrix, for a better exploitation of the matrix together with the textile, in the global performance of the NTRM composite system as a whole.

Non-linear FEA. A numerical model was used to simulate the behaviour of the tested systems and to derive preliminary τ -slip relationships. The bond characteristics could be simulated by means of a linear behaviour, due to the poor cohesion at the natural fiber to the mortar surface, confirming the yarn failure occurrence as well. This law can be used to calculate the bond behaviour of this natural composite with different geometries, varying the architecture reinforcements and their number of layers for the optimization of the composite characteristics in order to meet the strengthening needs.

Further work is currently underway to provide a better estimate of the damage parameters and enable the development of bond relationships that can define all stages of the τ -slip behaviour (initial adhesion and subsequent cohesion) in a more reliable manner.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

All papers shall include an author declaration of conflicts of interest; if there are no conflicts, please indicate this as follows:

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is available from the authors upon reasonable request.